

VeriFish Calendar

Delicious and
nutritious seafood
on your plate,
all year long

The information included in this calendar is sourced from the **FAO Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)** and **EuroFIR FoodEXplorer**, which includes more than 40 national food composition datasets.

The calendar's data is current up to April 2026.

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January

Meet the Species

Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) is one of the world's most important fish species. It is a predator in North Atlantic ecosystems and has long been central to commercial fisheries in Europe and North America. Widespread overfishing has caused major population declines, making Atlantic cod a powerful symbol of the need for sustainable fisheries management.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that cod can produce millions of eggs in a single spawning season?

This means healthy cod stocks can recover well when fishing is well managed, one reason why sustainable management really matters.

Sustainability Snapshot

Fish stock biomass means the total weight of all the fish of one kind in the sea (or in a lake) at a given time. Scientists use it to check whether there is plenty of fish or if a stock is getting too low. This is happening with too much fishing.

Atlantic Cod

Nutritional Highlights

Cod is a lean white fish, low in fat and high in protein. It provides vitamins like niacin (B3) and vitamin B12 and minerals, such as iodine and selenium.

Scientific Name:
Gadus morhua

Recipe of the Month: Cod Nuggets

Ingredients

650 g fresh cod; 30 g all-purpose flour; two large eggs; 1 tsp oregano; ½ tsp lemon zest; 75 g bread crumbs; oil (for brushing); salt & pepper

For serving

Ketchup, tartare sauce or lemon wedges

Steps

1. Preheat your oven to 220°C. Place a sheet of parchment paper on a big baking tray.
2. Cut the cod into small pieces, about the size of a walnut.
3. Put the cod pieces in a large bowl and sprinkle the flour over them. Mix gently until all the pieces are lightly coated.
4. In a shallow bowl, whisk the eggs with the lemon zest, salt, pepper seasoning and put the breadcrumbs in another shallow bowl.
5. Coat the fish: dip the floured cod pieces into the egg mixture. Let the extra egg drip off. Roll them in the breadcrumbs until they're covered and crunchy.
6. Place the coated cod pieces on the baking tray. Brush them with a little oil.
7. Bake for 20–25 minutes, until the nuggets are crispy and golden.

Add a tiny pinch of salt if you like, and serve with ketchup, tartare sauce, or lemon wedges.

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February

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28

Meet the Species

Northern prawns (*Pandalus borealis*), also known as **cold-water shrimp**, live in the cold waters of the North Atlantic. They are fast-growing, short-lived, and mainly harvested using bottom trawl nets. Typically sold cooked and peeled, frozen, or chilled, northern prawns are low in fat, high in protein, and rich in vitamins and minerals. They are prized for their sweet flavour and firm texture.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that Northern prawns are the basis for the iconic Swedish prawn sandwich *Räkmacka*?

It is typically made with North Atlantic cold-water prawns, hard-boiled eggs, lettuce, mayonnaise, and lemon/dill garnish. It is often served on rye bread or a toasted white bun.

Sustainability Snapshot

Bycatch is the unintended capture of non-target species, including juvenile fish and other marine life, which are often injured or die before or after being discarded.

Fisheries using small mesh sizes, such as shrimp and prawn fisheries, can have particularly high bycatch of young fish. Using special adaptation in the net can help to reduce bycatch by allowing unwanted species to escape and continue growing.

Northern Prawn

Nutritional Highlights

Northern Prawns are low in fat and rich in protein. They provide vitamins, such as vitamins E and B12, and minerals like selenium and iodine.

Scientific Name:

Pandalus borealis

Recipe of the Month: Grilled Shrimp Skewers

Ingredients

450 g large shrimp fresh or unfrozen, peeled; 2 bell peppers, cut into big chunks; 1 medium zucchini, cut into thick slices (about 1.5 cm); 60 ml olive oil; lemon juice (about 2 tbsp); ½ tsp garlic powder; ½ tsp salt; ½ tsp black pepper

Steps

Before you start place 8 wooden skewers in water for 30 minutes to avoid burning.

1. Make the marinade: whisk together the olive oil, lemon juice, garlic powder, salt and pepper.
2. Add the shrimp and veggies to the marinade, mix and set aside for 15 minutes.
3. Build the skewers: alternate between shrimp and vegetables.
4. Cook: place the skewers on a preheated grill. Cook each skewer 2-3 minutes per side. Shrimp should turn pink and opaque. Alternatively you can cook the skewers in the oven on a baking sheet: preheat to 220°C and bake for 6-8 minutes.

For nutritional, allergens and additional information, scan the QR code

March

Meet the Species

Sardines (*Sardina pilchardus*) are small schooling fish caught mainly with purse seine nets in the Mediterranean and Atlantic ocean. Their populations can fluctuate widely due to sensitivity to water temperature and food availability. Sardines are an affordable seafood rich in protein, omega-3 fatty acids, calcium, and vitamin D, and when well managed, their fast growth and reproduction make fisheries potentially sustainable.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that sardines are named after the island of Sardinia?

They were once so abundant there that they became deeply connected to local cuisine and Mediterranean fishing traditions.

Sustainability Snapshot

The **climate impact of food** reflects how much it contributes to climate change and is usually measured in CO₂-equivalents.

For seafood, fuel use during fishing is often the main source of emissions. Small pelagic fish such as sardines and anchovies have a very low climate impact, comparable to beans, making them an excellent low-impact source of protein and essential nutrients.

Sardine

Nutritional Highlights

Sardines are nutrient dense and provide high amounts of protein, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamin D, B-vitamins such as B12 and niacin (B3), and minerals like selenium, or calcium when eaten with the bones.

Scientific Name:

Sardina pilchardus

Recipe of the Month: Baked Breaded Sardines

Ingredients

240 g canned sardines in olive oil; 2 eggs; 40 g flour; 2 tbsp of parsley; 50 g breadcrumbs; 1 tbsp olive oil; a pinch of salt and pepper

Steps

1. Preheat your oven at 200°C before starting.
2. Carefully open the canned sardines and drain the oil with the help of a strainer, set them aside.
3. Prepare the egg wash by whisking eggs, parsley, salt and pepper.
4. Now coat your sardines: first in flour, then dip them into the egg wash and finally coat them in breadcrumbs.
5. Place each fillet on a baking tray, drizzle olive oil and bake them for 10 min at 200°C or until golden brown.
6. Once they are ready, pop them out of the oven, and plate them.

You can enjoy them just like in Spain, with a squeeze of lemon!

For nutritional, allergens and additional information, scan the QR code

April

Meet the Species

Trout (*Oncorhynchus spp*, *Salmo spp*) are related to salmon and a well known freshwater farmed fish species. **Rainbow trout** is the most common trout species. Like brown trout, rainbow trout may remain in freshwater throughout their life, or migrate to sea before returning to spawn.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that rainbow trout has been cultured since the late 19th century, making it one of the species with the longest presence in modern fish farming?

Rainbow trout have been spread globally for farming and angling, and are now present in eastern North America, Europe, South America, Africa, Asia and Australasia.

Sustainability Snapshot

Effluents released to the environment indicate pollution from fish farms, as waste and uneaten feed can accumulate. In freshwater systems such as trout farms, this is often managed through water treatment. Recirculating aquaculture systems are especially sustainable because they are closed systems, reducing pollution and limiting the risk of disease entry.

Rainbow Trout

Nutritional Highlights

The Rainbow Trout is rich in protein, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamin D, niacin (B3) and B12. It is also a good source of vitamin B6 and selenium.

Scientific Name:

Oncorhynchus mykiss

Recipe of the Month: Rainbow Trout Mac & Cheese

Ingredients

200 g rainbow fresh trout fillets (or thawed); 250 g macaroni pasta; 40 g butter; 5 g vegetable oil; 40 g all purpose flour; 600 ml milk; 200 g cheddar cheese shredded; 100 g liquid cream; ½ tsp garlic powder; salt & pepper

Steps

1. Cook the trout. Cut the fillets in small pieces, add salt, pepper and garlic powder and cook 3-4 minutes in a hot pan with a bit of cooking oil. Set aside.
2. Cook the macaroni following the package instructions.
3. Prepare the cheesy bechamel: in a medium pot, melt the butter, add the flour and mix. Slowly add the milk and cream while still stirring to avoid any lumps. Leave it to thicken at low heat. Once thick, add half of the shredded cheddar cheese and mix.
4. In an oven dish: add the macaroni, fish and sauce together and mix. Top with the other half of the shredded cheddar.
5. Bake in the oven for 20 min at 180°C.

Enjoy this delicious creamy and comforting dish!

For nutritional, allergens and additional information, scan the QR code

May

Meet the Species

Skipjack tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) is the most widely caught tuna species worldwide, mainly harvested with purse seine nets in tropical oceans. Its fast growth and high reproduction make stocks generally more resilient when well managed. Skipjack is the primary species used in canned tuna, valued for its affordability, wide availability, high protein and omega-3 content, and typically lower mercury levels than larger tuna species.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that sharks are a valuable bycatch for tuna fisheries? The fins are taken off and the body is thrown back in the sea. Shark finning regulations focus on banning the cruel practice of removing fins at sea, primarily through “**fins naturally attached**” (FNA) policies, like the EU's rule requiring fins to stay on the carcass until port.

Sustainability Snapshot

Bycatch of endangered species is often a problem in tropical areas with a high biodiversity. Sharks are often bycatch in longline fisheries for tuna. Some skipjack fisheries have a problem of bycatch of dolphins. Well managed fisheries, recognised by the MSC ecolabel, have measures in place to avoid this bycatch.

Skipjack Tuna

Nutritional Highlights

Skipjack Tuna is a nutrient dense fish. It is low in fat, but high in omega-3 fatty acids and protein, vitamin D, B-vitamins, and minerals like selenium.

Recipe of the Month: Tuna Dip

Ingredients

1 pack cream cheese (e.g. Philadelphia); 1 tuna tin in water; 2 tbsp lemon juice; pepper & salt to taste; chives (to top)

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Steps

This recipe is very quick:

1. Open and drain the tuna tin.
2. Mix all the ingredients together in a medium bowl until it's smooth: tuna, cream cheese, lemon juice, salt and pepper.
3. Top with chives.

It's ready!

You can eat it on toast, or dip in chopped cucumbers and carrots

Scientific Name:

Katsuwonus pelamis

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June

Meet the Species

Gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*), also known as **dorado**, is widely farmed in the Mediterranean in coastal sea cages with good water flow and fed formulated diets increasingly based on plant ingredients. Popular in Southern Europe and the Middle East, it is usually sold whole and enjoyed grilled, baked, or roasted for its mild flavour and firm white flesh.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that the golden stripe between the eyes was admired in ancient Greece and Rome? Thanks to this distinctive feature, which gives it the name **gilthead**, seabream was considered a luxury fish.

Sustainability Snapshot

Antimicrobial therapeutic treatments used: As in terrestrial animal farming, diseases can occur in fish farms, sometimes requiring **antimicrobial treatments**.

However, their use should be minimised, as antimicrobial resistance is a growing concern. Modern seabream farming is therefore increasingly regulated to reduce environmental impacts such as waste and disease.

Gilthead Seabream

Nutritional Highlights

Gilthead Seabream provides high amounts of protein, omega-3 fatty acids, and other key nutrients such as vitamin D, niacin (B3), vitamin B12, and selenium.

Recipe of the Month: Seabream Papillote

Ingredients

2 seabream fillets; 150 g cherry tomatoes; 50 g pitted black olives; ½ tsp of dried herbes de Provence mix; 1 tbsp of lemon juice; ½ tsp of garlic powder; 1 tbsp olive oil; pinch of salt and pepper

For nutritional, allergens and additional information, scan the QR code

Steps

1. Preheat your oven to 180°C and halve the cherry tomatoes and the black olives.
2. On an oven tray, place one large sheet of parchment paper over one of foil.
3. Put the fillets on the parchment paper with the rest of the dried ingredients.
4. Drizzle over the olive oil and the lemon juice. Now, seal the fillets by folding the spare parchment paper and foil over the fish.
5. Bake them in the oven for 15 min. Once ready, carefully take them out and open the parchment paper to let the steam escape.

Enjoy!

Scientific Name:

Sparus aurata

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July

Meet the Species

(European) Plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*) is a flatfish from the North-East Atlantic, North Sea, and Baltic Sea, mainly caught with bottom and beam trawls. Stocks are generally healthy when well managed. Prized for its mild white flesh, plaice is sold fresh, filleted, or frozen and prepared baked, fried, or grilled. Low in fat and rich in protein, B vitamins, and minerals, it is considered a relatively sustainable seafood when caught under regulated quotas.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that plaice starts life swimming upright like a normal fish, but as it grows, one eye slowly moves to the other side of its head?

As an adult, it lives flat on the seabed, perfectly camouflaged against sand.

Sustainability Snapshot

Fish living on or near the seafloor are often caught with heavy nets dragged along the seabed, which can strongly affect marine habitats and release stored carbon and nutrients. Depending on habitat sensitivity, complex seabeds may shift into flatter, simpler environments. The EU protects vulnerable areas through the **Natura 2000 network**, requiring Member States to adjust management, including possible bans on bottom-contact trawling.

(European) Plaice

Nutritional Highlights

Plaice is a flatfish that is low in fat, high in protein, and a good source of vitamin D, B-vitamins, selenium and iodine.

Scientific Name:

Pleuronectes platessa

Recipe of the Month: Plaice Tacos

Ingredients

Plaice fillet (4 medium fillets) or other white fish; 1/2 small lettuce; 1 avocado; 4 spring onions; coriander (or parsley) for topping; salt & pepper; 12 taco-sized corn or flour tortillas (35-30 g each)

For the sauce

120 g of Greek yogurt; 1 tbsp lime juice; 2 tbsp mild sriracha sauce (optional); 60 g mayonnaise; a pinch of salt

Steps

1. Prepare the sauce (add all ingredients together and mix) and set aside.
2. Cut the veggies: spring onion, avocado and lettuce.
3. Add salt and pepper on the raw fish.
4. Add the cooking oil in a pan. When the pan is hot, place the fish in and cook for 4 minutes (2 minutes on each side) or until opaque (very white).
5. Spread all the ingredients in one taco or small tortilla, and add one or two tablespoons of sauce and some coriander (or parsley).

Note: you can also use red cabbage instead of lettuce. Bon Appetit!

August

Meet the Species

Mussels (*Mytilus spp*) are bivalve shellfish farmed worldwide, especially in Europe, Asia, and North America, using rope culture or seafloor methods. They are eaten globally, often steamed, boiled, or added to soups and pasta, and are particularly popular in Europe. Mussels are low in fat, high in protein, and rich in omega-3 fatty acids, vitamin B12, and minerals such as iron, zinc, and selenium.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that mussels are natural water filters?

As they feed, they remove tiny particles and plankton, helping improve water clarity.

Mussels are among the most sustainable seafood choices in Europe, requiring no feed, fertilisers, or freshwater, and having a very low carbon footprint compared to most animal proteins.

Sustainability Snapshot

MSC (Marine Stewardship Council) and **ASC (Aquaculture Stewardship Council)** are widely regarded as reliable seafood ecolabels. They are independent, science-based, and strictly controlled, with full traceability required throughout the supply chain. Both schemes are **ISEAL Code Compliant**, meaning they meet the global benchmark for credible sustainability standards and are trusted by retailers and consumers worldwide.

Mussel

Nutritional Highlights

Mussels are a nutritious seafood, low in fat yet high in omega-3 fatty acids. They also provide high amounts of protein, vitamin B12 and are rich in minerals such as iron, zinc, selenium, and iodine.

Scientific Name:
Mytilus edulis

Recipe of the Month: Stuffed Mussels

Ingredients

1 kg mussels with shells; a sprig of parsley; 40 g breadcrumbs; 25 g parmesan cheese; 2 garlic cloves; 3 tbsp olive oil; 2 tbsp basil leaves (fresh) (or substitute it with 1 tsp of dried basil)

For nutritional, allergens and additional information, scan the QR code

Steps

1. Scrub the mussels under cold water and remove any beards (the stringy bits). Discard any mussels that are already open and don't close when tapped.
2. In a sauce pan, put water to boil. Once ready, carefully add the parsley sprig and mussels.
3. Let the mussels steam for 10 min, or until they open. In the meantime, preheat your oven at 200°C.
4. As they open, take them out of the sauce pan and place them on a plate. Use tongs as they are really hot. Discard any unopened shells.
5. Let's make the stuffing. Chop the garlic and basil. Now, in a bowl place the breadcrumbs, the cheese, the olive oil and the chopped garlic and basil.
6. Combine them all, the mixture should look like wet sand. With your hands stuff each half side of the mussels with the stuffing.
7. Place the stuffed mussels on a baking tray, drizzle olive oil on top and bake them for 10 minutes or until the stuffing gets golden brown.

September

Meet the Species

European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) is a demersal fish found in the Northeast Atlantic and the Mediterranean. It is mainly caught with bottom trawl nets, longlines, and gillnets. Hake is popular in Europe, especially Spain, Portugal, and Italy. Its white, delicate, and mild-flavoured flesh makes it suitable for baking, frying, grilling, or in stews. It is sold fresh, frozen, or filleted. Hake is low in fat, high in protein, and a good source of B vitamins, phosphorus, and selenium.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that next to European hake there is Argentinian hake, South African hake and Chilean hake? These are all different hake species. By checking the label, you can find out the species and where your fish is coming from.

Sustainability Snapshot

The origin and the official name of a seafood product is mandatory label information for fresh and frozen seafood products in the EU. For processed products, this is not mandatory. The label also has information whether the seafood is from wild capture or aquaculture and what the production method was.

European Hake

Nutritional Highlights

Hake is a lean, protein-rich fish and a good source of vitamins and minerals, including vitamin B12, niacin (B3), iodine, and selenium.

For nutritional, allergens and additional information, scan the QR code

Recipe of the Month: Hake in Tomato Sauce

Ingredients

6 medium fillets skinless and boneless hake fillets; 2 tbsp fresh parsley leaves; 2 tbsp of olive oil; 2 garlic cloves, chopped; 400 g of tinned tomatoes; 1 tsp sugar; ½ tsp lemon zest; 1 tsp turmeric; 1 tsp chilli flakes; 100 ml water; salt & pepper

Steps

1. Combine all the ingredients for the sauce in a large pan and cook until it simmers (when you see small bubbles).
2. Add the hake fillets, cover and cook for 15 minutes.
3. Serve on top of mashed potatoes, top with fresh parsley and enjoy!

Scientific Name:

Merluccius merluccius

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October

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	31				

Meet the Species

Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) is the most widely farmed salmon species, mainly produced in Norway, Chile, Scotland, and Ireland in coastal sea cages and fed formulated diets increasingly based on plant ingredients.

It is one of the world's most popular fish, eaten fresh, smoked, canned, or frozen, and is a key ingredient in dishes such as sushi and grilled meals. Atlantic salmon is high in protein and rich in omega-3 fatty acids, vitamin D, and B vitamins.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that salmon convert feed into edible protein much more efficiently than land animals such as pigs or cattle? This means that less feed is needed to produce the same amount of food.

Sustainability Snapshot

Maximum stocking density (kg/m³) is relevant in aquaculture because it directly affects fish welfare, environmental impact, and farm performance. Setting a maximum density helps ensure fish have enough space, oxygen, and good water quality. Maximum stocking density limits are a clear, measurable welfare indicator.

Atlantic Salmon

Nutritional Highlights

Atlantic Salmon is an oily fish that provides high amounts of omega-3 fatty acids, protein, selenium, vitamin D and B-vitamins such as niacin (B3), vitamin B6 and B12.

Scientific Name:
Salmo salar

Recipe of the Month: Salmon Wellington

Ingredients

2 large rectangular sheets of puff pastry; 450 g fresh salmon fillet without skin; 120 g spinach; 1 garlic clove, chopped; 1 tsp lemon juice; 2 tsp mild mustard; 1 tsp honey; 1 egg; 1 tbsp olive oil; ½ tsp salt

Steps

1. Cook the veggies: heat a pan and add 1 tbsp olive oil. Add the garlic and spinach and cook until soft. Add one tsp lemon and a pinch of salt and set aside.
2. Make the honey-mustard sauce: in a small bowl, mix the mustard and the honey.
3. Cut the salmon in 8 pieces.
4. Prepare the puff pastry: cut it into 8 rectangles, on each, put a spoon of the spinach mix in the middle, add one piece of salmon and spread a bit of the honey-mustard sauce on the salmon and a pinch of salt.
5. Cut the second puff pastry into 8 rectangles and add each on top of each salmon piece.
6. Now cut it in a fish shape and seal each side with a fork.
7. Cut diagonal lines: use a small knife to score the top of the pastry by cutting very shallow diagonal lines. Then score diagonal lines the other way to make a crosshatch pattern (Don't cut all the way through!).
8. Beat the egg and brush the top with the mixture.
9. Place each fish on a baking parchment in a baking tray. Bake for 15-18 minutes, until golden brown.

Let cool for a few minutes and serve warm.

For nutritional, allergens and additional information, scan the QR code

November

Meet the Species

Squid (*Loligo spp.*, *Illex spp.*) are fast-growing, short-lived cephalopods found in oceans worldwide, with major fisheries in the Atlantic, Pacific, and Indian Oceans. They are mainly caught using jigging or trawl nets, often at night when they move closer to the surface. Squid populations can vary greatly from year to year due to environmental conditions, but their short life cycle makes them relatively resilient to fishing pressure when fisheries are well managed.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that many squid populations are increasing as oceans warm, because they grow fast and adapt quickly? Most squid live only **1-2 years**, but they grow incredibly fast during that time. Some species go from tiny hatchlings to full-grown predators in just months.

Sustainability Snapshot

Preventing forced labour, modern slavery and human trafficking is a key socio-economic issue in fisheries and aquaculture. Human rights abuses have been reported in distant-water squid fleets with limited oversight, where migrant crew from countries such as Indonesia and the Philippines face long hours, withheld wages, debt bondage and confiscated documents. As a result, some squid on global markets may come from vessels linked to serious rights violations, while squid from European waters carries a much lower risk.

European Squid

Nutritional Highlights

The European Squid is a cephalopod that is high in omega-3 fatty acids and high-quality protein. It is also a good source of vitamin E, niacin (B3), vitamin B12, zinc, selenium and iodine.

Scientific Name:
Loligo vulgaris

Recipe of the Month: Crispy Baked Squid Rings

Ingredients

500 g squid tube; 100 g breadcrumbs; 125 g cornflour; 1/2 tsp baking powder; 20 g olive oil; 2 eggs; salt & pepper

Steps

Before starting, preheat the oven to 180°C.

1. Slice the tube into rings, try to make them as wide as a finger.
2. Set three different plates, in the first, put in the corn flour with baking powder, in the second the eggs and, in the third the breadcrumbs.
3. Whisk the eggs, salt and pepper until they start to foam.
4. Now it's time to roll up your sleeves, and coat the rings! First, dredge each ring in the corn flour, tapping off any excess. Then dip it in the egg mixture. Finally, coat it thoroughly with breadcrumbs for extra crunch.
5. Repeat the process for all the rings.
6. Place the coated rings on a baking tray lined with parchment paper, brush each with olive oil, and bake for 15-20 minutes, or until golden brown.
7. Remove them from the oven, then plate and serve with mayonnaise and freshly squeezed lemon juice.

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December

Meet the Species

Brown crab (*Cancer pagurus*), also called edible crab, is mainly caught with baited pots or creels, a selective method with low seabed impact. In the North Sea, it is largely a targeted pot fishery.

Brown crab is prized for its sweet, firm meat, which is low in fat, high in protein, and rich in minerals, B vitamins, and omega-3 fatty acids. Pot fisheries are generally considered sustainable due to low bycatch and minimal seabed disturbance.

Did You Know That...?

Did you know that brown crabs thrive in offshore wind farms (OWFs)?

The turbine foundations create artificial reefs, providing complex hard-substrate habitat (rocks, mussels, anemones) that contrasts with the surrounding sandy seabed, attracting and concentrating them, even acting as nurseries.

Sustainability Snapshot

Fishing mortality is a measure of how many fish are taken out of that population by fishing, either by being caught directly or through fishing gear like nets or hooks.

If too many fish are caught, there might not be enough left to reproduce, which could cause the population to shrink or collapse over time.

The Fishing Mortality indicator helps scientists and fisheries managers figure out how many fish can be safely caught each year without harming the long-term health of fish stocks.

Brown Crab

Nutritional Highlights

Brown Crab meat is low in fat, high in protein, vitamin B12, zinc, selenium, and a good source of riboflavin (B2) and magnesium.

Scientific Name:

Cancer pagurus

Recipe of the Month: Crab Cakes

Ingredients

1 large egg, beaten; 80 g mayonnaise; 2 tbsp mild mustard; a splash of mild sriracha sauce (or other hot sauce) (optional); salt & pepper; 450 g cooked crabmeat; 70 g breadcrumbs; 2 tbsp fresh parsley (optional); a little oil for frying

Steps

1. Mix the wet ingredients: in a medium bowl mix together egg + mayonnaise + mustard + tiny splash hot sauce + pinch of salt and pepper.
2. Add the crab meat, breadcrumbs and parsley to the mixture and mix.
3. Shape the patties: scoop a handful and press them into little patties (like mini burgers). If it feels too wet, add a bit of breadcrumbs.
4. Cook: heat a little oil in a pan over medium heat, cook the patties for 3 to 4 minutes per side until golden.

Transfer to a plate and serve warm with lemon wedges and a mild dip (mayo, tartare sauce, etc.)

Tip: You can also serve the crab cakes with a green salad on the side!

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